

Cactus as a Medicinal Plant: A Review

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Abstract

The Cactus is one of the most widely distributed plants in the xeric environment and has special characteristics. The major species of cacti used for livestock include opuntia ficus-indica Mill. opuntia lindheimeri Engelm, opuntia ellisiana, opuntia engelmannii Salm Dyck, opuntia chrysacantha Berg, opuntia amyclae, opuntia rastrera Weber, opuntia stricta Haw, and Nopalea cochenillifera Salm Dyck. Cactus species are plants that grow in the arid and semiarid regions of the world. Certain opuntia species are found in the wild, and while the fruit of these species is unfit for human consumption, the plants can serve as animal fodder. Its composition includes essential nutrients including taurine and betalains, as well as minerals, vitamins, and antioxidants. As a result, the food and nutraceutical industries can make great and diverse value-added products from it.

Keywords: Cactus, Opuntia, Cactus pear, Cactaceae, Antioxidant, Physico-chemical Composition, Pharmacological Properties.

Introduction

Drylands occupy approximately 40 % of terrestrial surface and 2 billion people live in these areas. Furthermore, in certain parts of the world, climate change is raising temperatures as well as the frequency and intensity of droughts (FAO, 2019). A valuable source of fodder for dry and semiarid areas is cacti. The wild cactus population in Mexico determines the use of cacti as fodder. In other countries such as Brazil, Tunisia, South Africa, and Morocco, cactus fodder is produced in cultivated orchards, which could have a multi-use purpose (fruit/forage/industrial processed products) or only fodder. For ruminants and other types of animals, it provides energy and water,

especially during the dry season of the year. In semiarid areas, cacti serve as a reserve of live fodder and are a valuable resource for boosting food security (Ben Salem et al., 2002). Even in environments where other forms of fodder are limited, cacti yield a large quantity of succulent biomass with a good palatability (Ben Salem et al., 2002). Cacti use a photosynthetic process called cactus acid metabolism, or CAM (Leegood, 2013). Cacti often have lower dry matter concentrations (5–15% DM), crude protein, and fibre (ADF, acid detergent fibre, and NDF, neutral detergent fibre). They also typically have higher digestibility than other forages found in warm climates. (Batista et al.,

2009; Monteiro et al., 2018; In´Acio et al., 2020) .The term Cactus is derived from an ancient Greek word ‘kaktos’, which was used by Theophrastus to demarcate the spiny plants. Since cacti are the most common wild and ornamental plant in the Cactaceae family, they are very valuable economically. 'New world' plants is another name for them (Shetty et al., 2012). Because it contains 14% glucose, it is also regarded as an energy source (Salim et al., 2009).It displays CAM metabolism physiologically, which primarily has a mechanism to withstand environmental stress. Lack of access to water (Gibson and Nobel, 1986; Anderson, 2001; Bensadón et al., 2010). Cacti's stems undergo morphological modification to become fleshy, flat, cylindrical, or globular, and to form cladodes. Bats, birds, and insects assist in pollination

and seed distribution (Gibson and Nobel, 1986; Godúnez-Alvarez et al., 2002; Godý´nez-Alvarez, 2004). Cacti, also known as cactuses or cactus, are a unique type of plant that is found in dry regions all over the world. The Cactaceae family, which includes 124 genera and 1438 species worldwide, is mostly found in tropical regions (Del Socorro Santos-Díaz and Camarena-Rangel, 2019). For example, even before Christopher Columbus arrived in America, cactus was used as food, medicine, and cosmetics (Lema-Rumińska and Kulus, 2014; Shetty, Rana, and Preetham, 2012). Some commercial items are made primarily from cactus species, like soaps and shampoos. De Lucena et al. (2013) suggest that food items such as cakes, biscuits, sweets, puddings, and candies can be obtained from cactus.

Table No.1: Scientific Classification

Kingdom	Plantae
Clade	Tracheophytes
Clade	Angiosperms
Clade	Eudicots
Order	Caryophyllales
Family	Cactaceae
Subfamilies	Cactoideae Maihuenioideae Opuntioideae pereskioideae

The History of Succulents and Cacti

The Name's Origin

The word "cactus" is derived from the Greek word "kaktos," which was a general term for the Native American Cactaceae and was used to refer to a species of thorny thistle in classical Greek. The remarkable capacity of

succulent plants to hold onto water is why they got their name.

The Past Eternal

Since the time of the Incas in Peru and the Aztecs in Mexico, cacti and succulents have been known about. They saw them as a vital sign for divination, beauty items, healing, and feeling at one with their gods. Mexico City

was once known as Tenochtitlan, which translates to "place of the sacred cactus." They may have used plant representations as decorations on their structures, ceramics, and other uncovered artefacts.

European Discoveries

It wasn't until the 14th and 15th centuries that cacti garnered serious scientific attention. The first melocactus was introduced to Europe by Christopher Columbus. Since the plants he found are native to the Americas, they are referred to as "New World Plants." On the other hand, every continent that supports life has cacti and succulents. Aloes and other "Old World Plants" are present in Africa.

Various Uses of Cactus

Cactus Use as Fruit

The fruits of cactus vary in weight from 50 to 150 gm depending on the environmental conditions and its origin. It's an elongated, oval-shaped berry. The pulp is the edible portion of the extremely thick pericarp. It is mostly composed of water (84–90%) and reducing sugar (10–15%). *Opuntia ficus indica* fruits are consumed in many different ways. The fruit is often referred to as pitaya or "dragon fruit." Some cacti, like *Opuntia tuna*, *Opuntia streptacantha*, and *Opuntia cardona*, are frequently farmed for their fruit. Because of their high pH (which ranges from 5.3 to 7.1) and low acidity, cactus fruits have a limited shelf life. (2012), Shetty et al. Fruits contain nutrients, vitamins, and amino acids. Typically, 54.18% of the fruit is edible (Bekir, 2004). Within cacti are betalains.

Cactus Use as Vegetables

The young or tender vegetative parts of wild cactus which lack glochids and spines are used as vegetables and salads (Russell and Felker, 1987)

Cactus Use as Fodder

In regions where there is a risk of drought, the spines are burned and fed to cattle. Despite having a low protein level, it is used as dairy cattle fodder in semi-arid climates. It imparts good flavour to milk and imparts good colour to butter (Salimetal, 2009).

Traditional Uses of Cactus Plant

Different parts of *Opuntia monacantha* Haw. Can be used to treat different types of diseases. Its fruit is used to cure gonorrhoea and syphilis; its mucilage is used to treat piles, pox strains, rheumatism, and leprosy; its stem is used as a cathartic and to treat diarrhoea. Its latex is used to treat constipation (Arshad et al., 2014; Chetry et al., 2018). The fruit of *Opuntia ficus-indica* is used in Italy as a diuretic, and for digestive disorders, while in Mexico it is used to treat wounds; in Morocco to treat stretch marks and wrinkles; in Turkey for joint dislocation, tonsillitis, and anemia; in India as an antispasmodic, diuretic, emollient, astringent, treatment for diarrhea, colitis, irritable bowel syndrome, and benign prostatic hypertrophy; (Ahmet Sargin, 2015; de la Cruz, Malpartida, Santiago, Jullian, and Bourdy0, 2014; Erbay, Anıl, and Melikoğlu, 2016; Khan and Ahmad, 2015; Maroyi, 2017; Messaoudi et al., 2015; Pandita, Pandita, and Pandita, 2013; T. Tuttolomondo et al., 2014). In Peru for liver and kidney inflammation. Only amoeba, catarrh, cough, and whooping cough were treated with *melocactus bahiensis* (Britton and

Rose) Luetzelb, a plant primarily found in northern and eastern Brazil (de Lucena et al., 2013). *Opuntia engelmannii* Salm-CTDyck ex Engelm is common in south-central and southwestern United States and northern Mexico. Its use as a medicinal plant for diabetes was only reported in Mexico (Estrada-Castillón et al., 2018).

Medicinal Uses

- **The Anti-cancer properties of cacti**

The cactus pear fruit extract demonstrated its anti-cancer properties by preventing the growth of in vitro cell lines that represent bladder, ovarian, and cervical cancer. (Camacho-Chab et al., 2016).

- **Antioxidant effect**

The fruits and vegetative parts of different varieties of cactus, largely *Opuntia* contains many antioxidants. Examples include taurine, cysteine, reduced glutathione, ascorbic acid, and flavonoids including isorhamnetin, kaempferol, and quercetin (Tesoriere et al., 2005)

- **Antiviral effect**

The cactus stem extract of *Opuntia streptacantha* has the ability to inhibit the intracellular replication of DNA and RNA viruses in both people and animals, including HIV, equine herpes virus, pseudorabies virus, influenza virus, and herpes simplex virus type 2 (Ahmad et al., 1996).

- **Anti-inflammatory effect**

Because of its analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, genus *Opuntia* has been employed. *Opuntia dillenii* fruit extract

(Loro et al., 1999) and lyophilized cladodes have both been used for their anti-inflammatory properties.

- **Antidiabetic effect**

Italian herbalists are now employing species of *Opuntia* to lower blood sugar levels (Cicero et al., 2004). On non-diabetic rats, diabetic induced rats, and diabetic humans, the prickly pear extract has a hypoglycemic effect (Ibanez-Camacho et al., 1979; Ibanez-Camacho et al., 1983; Frati-Munari et al., 1988; Frati et al., 1990).

- **Anti-hyperlipidemic and hypercholesterolemic effect**

The consumption of cactus pear extract lowers cholesterol in humans and modifies low density lipoprotein (LDL) (Gurbachan and Felker, 1998; Fernandez et al., 1992; Frati, 1990; Stintzing et al., 2001; Stintzing and Carle, 2006)

Cholesterol

Both the cactus pad and the fruit of the cactus are high in fiber, which can lower cholesterol levels in the blood.

Blood sugar

According to some research, individuals who regularly consumed cactus pads had lower blood sugar levels than those who did not. To ascertain the causes of this, more investigation is required.

Immune system

Vitamin C is one of the best things for boosting the immune system, and cactus fruits are a great source of it. Frequent vitamin C

dosages boost white blood cell synthesis, which aids in the body's ability to combat viruses.

Digestion

Cacti have high potassium and betalain content, which is beneficial for digestion. While betalains are anti-inflammatory and aid in the protection of your digestive tract, potassium aids in the body's absorption of nutrients.

Pharmacological Properties of Cactus Plant

- **Antimicrobial potential**

Opuntia ficus-indica cladode extract, both immature and mature, shown antibacterial efficacy against both Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella enterica* ser. Typhimurium *Enterobacter aerogenes*) and Gram-positive bacteria (*Enterococcus faecalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*). (Blando, Russo, Negro, De Bellis, and Frassinetti, 2019). Seed oils from *Opuntia albicarpa* and *Opuntia ficus-indica* exhibited antibacterial activities against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and antifungal activity against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Candida albicans* (Ramírez-Moreno et al., 2017). The methanolic leaf extract of *Pereskia grandifolia* exhibited antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and Philip et al. (2009) identified *Bacillus subtilis*.

- **Antiviral potential**

Opuntia streptacantha's cladode extract shown antiviral activity against human

immunodeficiency virus, herpes simplex, horse herpes, pseudorabies, influenza, and respiratory syncytial viruses, as well as both DNA and RNA viruses. The extract rendered the extracellular virus inactive and prevented the production of the intracellular virus. (Ahmad, Davies, Randall, and Skinner, 1996).

- **Antioxidant Capacity**

The by-products obtained from cladodes and fruits of *Opuntia ficus-indica* exhibited antioxidant potential as studied by ABTS and FRAP assays (Bensadón, Hervert-Hernández, Sáyago-Ayerdi, and Goñi, 2010). The antioxidant potential is attributed mainly to the existence of phenolic substances like as ferulic acid, rutin, and isorhamnetin, etc. that are effective radical scavengers Galati, Enza Maria, and others (2003).

- **Antidiabetic potential**

The effect of antidiabetes can be Assigned to the partial reduction of D-glucose intestinal absorption, free radicals quenching, and inhibition of pancreatic β -cells injuries. The aforementioned actions could be caused by the oil that contains oleic and linoleic acids. Similarly, a number of additional investigations have shown that *Opuntia ficus-indica* crude extracts and cooked cactus stems can lower plasma, serum insulin, and postprandial glycemia. glucose-dependent insulinotropic peaks in the diabetic patient (López-Romero et al., 2014; Roman-Ramos, Flores-Saenz, and Alarcon-Aguilar, 1995).

- **Anti-Ulcer Potential**

The methanolic root extract of *Opuntia ficus-indica* f. *inermis* demonstrated gastro protective ability against an ethanol-induced

ulcer in rats (Alimi et al., 2010). The lyophilized cladodes of *Opuntia ficus-indica* were reported for their anti-ulcer potential in ethanol-induced ulcer in rats. The ultrastructural observations of gastric mucosa revealed the protective action of cladode against ethanol-induced ulcers. *Opuntia ficus-indica*'s mucilage may have a protective effect (E. M. Galati, Monforte, Tripodo, d'Aquino, and Mondello, 2001).

- **Potential for Cardio protection**

Taking *Opuntia ficus-indica* ingestion dried leaves exhibited a rapid increase in HDL cholesterol levels concomitantly with a decrease in LDL cholesterol and triglycerides in women affected with metabolic syndrome, indicating the hypocholesterolemic. As per Linares, Thimonier, and Degre (2007), the herb has an effect. According to the results of the randomised clinical trials (RCT) study, *Opuntia ficus indica* supplementation reduced blood pressure, total cholesterol, body fat percentage, and cardiovascular risk factors (Onakpoya, O'Sullivan, and Heneghan, 2015).

- **Neuroprotective potential**

The polysaccharide extracted from *Opuntia milpa* also exhibited neuroprotective activity against cerebral cortex and hippocampal slices from H₂O₂-induced injury by normalization of neuroprotective biochemical markers like acetate dehydrogenase (LDH), superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione (GSH), and total antioxidant competence (T-AOC) level (Xianju Huang, Li, Guo, and Yan, 2008). The polysaccharides isolated from *Opuntia dillenii* exhibited neuroprotective activities against brain ischemia-reperfusion injury in rats under in vivo conditions and.

They reduced the oxidative stress-induced damage in the PC12 cells under in vitro conditions (X. Huang, Li, Li, and Guo, 2009). The methanol extract of *Opuntia ficus-indica* furthermore induces neuronal changes in cultures of mouse cortical cells and has a neuroprotective effect against N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA), kainate (KA), and OGD oxygen deprivation oxygen (J. H. Kim et al., 2006).

Cactus's Nutritional Importance

Many names for the *Opuntia* species exist in the many countries where it is found. Nochtli is the original name in the Náhuatl language. Nevertheless, the fruit and shrub were renamed by the Spanish as higo de las Indias (now known as higo chumbo) and chumbera, respectively. It is referred to as ficod'India in Italy, figue de Barbarie in France, and prickly pear in Australia, South Africa, and the US. In an attempt to lessen the negative connotation of the word "prickly," which means "with spines," this is gradually changing into the moniker "cactus pear." It is referred to as sabras in Israel, which translates to "spiny outside but sweet inside." It is referred to as beles in Ethiopia and Eritrea. Depending on the location, it is referred known as nagphani, andatorra, or chapathi balli in various dialects around India. Because it is mostly used for animal feed, it is known as Palma forrageira in Brazil. Sudzuki et al., 1993.

Physico-Chemical Composition

Vitamin

The predominant components, comprising approximately 80% of the total vitamin E content present in fruit pulp, are the vitamin E

homologues, or isoforms gamma- and delta-tocopherol. Antioxidant properties of vitamin E are widely recognised for their potential to enhance the stability of fatty oils. The third main vitamin in cactus pears is ascorbic acid. (Stintzing and Other People, 2000).

Amino Acid

Proline, taurine, and serine are particularly abundant in cactus fruits (Uchoa and colleagues, 1998), while glutamine is the main amino acid found in cactus cladodes, followed by leucine, lysine, valine, arginine, phenylalanine, and isoleucine. Fruit pulp and seeds are excellent providers of proteins and amino acids (El-Mostafa and colleagues 2014).

Mineral Contents

Mineral content of cactus (mg/100g)

Table No.2: Source - El-Mostafa and others 2014

Mineral	Fruit pulp	cladode
Calcium	27.6	5.64 – 17.95
Calcium carbonate	--	11.5 - 14.3
Magnesium.	27.7.	8.80
Sodium.	0.8	0.3-0.4
Potassium.	161	2.35-55.20
Iron.	1.5.	0.09
Phosphorus.	--	0.15-2.59
Zinc.	--	0.08
Manganese	--	0.19-0.29

- **Nutrients per serving**
A. 1-cup serving of raw, unsalted cactus contains:
- Calories: 24
- Protein: 1.98 grams

- Fat: 0.135 grams
- Carbohydrates: 5 grams
- Fiber: 3.3 grams
- Sugar: 1.72 grams
- (<https://www.webmd.com/diet/health-benefits-cactus>)

Cultivation

- **propagation of Opuntia or cactus plants**
Pick edible Opuntia plants that are close to your field. Opuntia is simply plants that are edible cacti. Cut the Opuntia plant's leaf or a few flat leaves, and then put them in your

cactus farm. It yields new plants in a matter of days, and as soon as the plant reaches the vegetative phase, flowering follows.

- **Harvesting in Cactus Farm**

The plant is harvested when it reaches a height of 4 to 6 metres. In order to preserve the cactus leaves' shelf life, gather the flattened leaves during certain times and pack the leaves right away. Cactus leaves do,

.Bioactive Extractable Substance

Figure No.1: Bioactive Extractable Substance

The extensive body of research indicates that the most common methods for extracting bioactive compounds from cactus plants (fruit pulp and peel, seeds, cladodes, leaves, and flowers) are conventional extraction techniques using organic solvents. However, reports of the application of cutting-edge methods such as SFE (Fathordoobady et al., 2019; Sharif et al., 2015), ultrasound-assisted extraction (Espinosa Muñoz et al., 2017), and sonication (Mena et al., 2018; Moussa-Ayoub et al., 2014) have also been made. Many studies detailed the extraction of bioactive compounds, primarily phenolics and betalains, from *Opuntia* spp. fruits employing

however, have a longer shelf life than other crops. [https://www.agrifarming.in/cactus-farming-cultivation-practices-of-cactus#:~:text=](https://www.agrifarming.in/cactus-farming-cultivation-practices-of-cactus#:~:text=The%20only%20thing%20you%20need%20is%20a%20certain%20amount%20of%20water%20and%20upkeep) The only thing you need is a certain amount of water and upkeep

solvents such as acetone (Kıvrak et al., 2018), methanol: water (60:40), ethanol: formic acid: water (50:5:45 v/v/v) (Albano et al., 2015), and Among other things, methanol (80%) was acidified with 1% formic acid (Mena et al., 2018).

- **Various Cactus Types**

1. Angel Wing
2. Cacti of the African milk tree
3. A plant of Christmas cactus
4. Cactus ladyfinger
5. Cactus Parado
6. Rat tail cactus

Figure No. 2: Angel wing

Figure No. 3: African milk tree

Figure No. 4: Christmas cactus

Figure No. 5: Ladyfinger Cactus

Figure No. 6: Parodia cactus

Figure No.7: Rat tail cactus

Conclusion

A cactus is a multipurpose plant that can be used as a fruit, vegetable, fodder, and for traditional purposes as well as for industrial processing. It requires little water to thrive. The cactus' scientific categorization and name origin are also part of its history. The medicinal properties of cacti include their anti-inflammatory, antiviral, antioxidant, anti-cancer, and antidiabetic properties.

Additionally, cacti have an impact on immune system function, digestion, blood sugar, and cholesterol. Cacti's pharmacological qualities,

including its antibacterial, antiviral, antioxidant, antiulcer, and neuroprotective potentials, are disclosed.

Cacti are a source of vitamins, amino acids, carbs, fibres, protein, and calories. There was also mention of cactus cultivation and extraction. The many cactus species were also introduced.

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Reference

1. FAO, 2019. *Trees, forests and land use in drylands: the first global assessment – full report*. FAO Forestry Paper No. 184. Rome.
2. Ben Salem, H., Nefzaoui, A., Ben Salem, L., 2002. Supplementing spineless cactus (*Opuntia ficus indica* f. *inermis*) based diets with urea-treated straw or oldman saltbush (*Atriplex nummularia* L.). *Effects on intake, digestion and growth*. *J. Agric. Sci.* 138, 85–92.
3. Leegood, R.C., 2013. *Photosynthesis*. In: Lennarz, W.J., Lane, M.D. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Biological Chemistry*. Academic Press, Cambridge, pp. 492–496.
4. Batista, A.M.V., Ribeiro Neto, A.C., Lucena, R.B., Santos, D.C., Dubeux Jr., J.C.B., Mustafa, A.F., 2009. Chemical composition and ruminal degradability of spineless cactus grown in Northeastern Brazil. *Rang. Ecol. Man.* 62, 297–301.
5. Monteiro, C.C.F., Ferreira, M.A., Veras, A.S.C., Guido, S.I., Almeida, M.P., Silva, R.C., Inacio, J.G., 2018. A new cactus variety for dairy cows in areas infested with *Dactylopius opuntiae*. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 59, 479–485.
6. Inacio, J.G., Conceição, M.G., Santos, D.C., Oliveira, J.C.V., Chagas, J.C.C., Moraes, G.S.O., Silva, E.T.S., Ferreira, M.A., 2020. Nutritional and performance viability of cactus *Opuntia*-based diets with different concentrate levels for Girolando lactating dairy cows. *Asian. Australas. J. Anim. Sci.* 33, 35–43.
7. Shetty, A. A.; Rana, M. K. and Preetham, S. P. (2012). Cactus: A medicinal food. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 49(5):530-536.
8. Salim, N.; Abdelwaheb, C.; Rabah, C. and Ahcene, B. (2009). Chemical composition of *Opuntia ficus-indica* (L.) fruit. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 8(8):1623-1624.
9. Gibson, A. C. and Nobel, P. S. (1986). *Cactus Primer*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge.
10. Anderson, E.F. (2001). *The cactus family*. Portland. Timber Press, Incorporated; First Edition edition , pp:776.
11. Bensadón, S.; Hervert-Hernández, D.; Sáyago-Ayerdi, S. G. and Goñi, I. (2010). By-products of *Opuntia ficus-indica* as a source of antioxidant dietary fiber. *Plant Foods for Human Nutrition*, 65(3):210-216.
12. Godínez-Álvarez, H. (2004). Pollination and seed dispersal by lizards: A review. *Revista Chilena de Historia Natural*, 77(3):569-577.
13. Godínez-Alvarez, H.; Valiente-Banuet, A. and Rojas-Martínez, A. (2002). The role of seed dispersers in the population dynamics of the columnar cactus *Neobuxbaumia tetetzo*. *Ecology*, 83(9):2617-2629.

14. del Socorro Santos-Díaz, M., and Camarena-Rangel, N. G. (2019). Cacti for production of metabolites: current state and perspectives. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 103(21-22), 8657-8667.
15. Lema-Rumińska, J., and Kulus, D. (2014). Micropropagation of Cacti—a Review. *Haseltonia*, 2014(19), 46-63, 18.
16. Shetty, A. A., Rana, M., and Preetham, S. (2012). Cactus: a medicinal food. *Journal of food science and technology*, 49(5), 530-536.
17. de Lucena, C. M., de Lucena, R. F. P., Costa, G. M., Carvalho, T. K. N., da Silva Costa, G. G., da Nóbrega Alves, R. R., . . . Quirino, Z. G. M. (2013). Use and knowledge of Cactaceae in Northeastern Brazil. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 9(1), 62.
18. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cactus>
19. https://www.theinkrag.com/cactus_corner_project/historycc.html
20. <https://images.app.goo.gl/6WeWFzRZiqtLF3BW7>
21. Bekir, E.A. (2004). Cactus pear (*Opuntia ficus-indica* Mill.) in Turkey: growing regions and pomological traits of cactus pear fruits. In: *Vth International Congress on Cactus Pear and Cochineal*, 728:51-54.
22. Stintzing, F. C. and Carle, R. (2005). Cactus stems (*Opuntia* spp.): A review on their chemistry, technology, and uses. *Molecular Nutrition and Food Research*, 49(2):175-194.
23. <https://images.app.goo.gl/1a5zxcwWkPjUq8x56600>
24. Russell, C. E. and Felker, P. (1987). The prickly-pears (*Opuntia* spp., Cactaceae): A source of human and animal food in semiarid regions. *Economic Botany*, 41(3):433-445.
25. <https://images.app.goo.gl/TEvGyjBNXDyV5xq97>
26. Arshad, M., Ahmad, M., Ahmed, E., Saboor, A., Abbas, A., and Sadiq, S. (2014). An ethnobiological study in Kala Chitta hills of Pothwar region, Pakistan: multinomial logit specification. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 10(1), 13.
27. Chetry, L. B., Basar, K., Taye, K., Taka, T., Tsering, J., and Wangpan, T. (2018). Medicinal Plants used against gastrointestinal disorders among the Adi Tribe of Eastern Himalaya. In: *Nebio*.
28. Ahmet Sargin, S. (2015). Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants in Bozyazı district of Mersin, Turkey. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 173, 105-126.
29. de la Cruz, M. G., Malpartida, S. B., Santiago, H. B., Jullian, V., and Bourdy, G. (2014). Hot and cold: medicinal plant uses in Quechua speaking communities in the high Andes (Callejón de Huaylas, Ancash, Perú). *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 155(2), 1093-1117.
30. Erbay, M., Anil, S., and Melikoğlu, G. (2016). Plants used in traditional treatment against anemia in Turkey. *Marmara Pharmaceutical Journal*, 20(2), 164-171.
31. Khan, M. P., and Ahmad, M. (2015). Traditional preference of Wild Edible Fruits (WEFs) for digestive disorders (DDs) among the indigenous communities of Swat Valley-Pakistan. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 174, 339-354.
32. Maroyi, A. (2017). Diversity of use and local knowledge of wild and cultivated plants in the Eastern Cape province, South Africa. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 13(1), 43.
33. Pandita, D., Pandita, A., and Pandita, S. (2013). Herbaceous medicinal and therapeutic plants of district samba of jammu province, jammu and kashmir (India). *Int J Indig Med Plants*, 46, 2051-4263.
34. Tuttolomondo, T., Licata, M., Leto, C., Gargano, M. L., Venturella, G., and La Bella, S. (2014). Plant genetic resources and traditional knowledge on medicinal use of wild shrub and herbaceous plant species in the Etna Regional Park (Eastern Sicily, Italy). *J Ethnopharmacol*, 155(2), 1362-1381.
35. Estrada-Castillón, E., Villarreal-Quintanilla, J. Á., Rodríguez-Salinas, M. M., Encinas-Domínguez, J. A., González-Rodríguez, H., Figueroa, G. R., and Arévalo, J. R. (2018). Ethnobotanical Survey of Useful Species in Bustamante, Nuevo León, Mexico. *Human Ecology*, 46(1), 117-132.
36. Salim, N.; Abdelwaheb, C.; Rabah, C. and Ahcene, B. (2009). Chemical composition of *Opuntia ficus-indica* (L.) fruit. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 8(8):1623-1624.
37. Camacho-Chab, J.; Lango-Reynoso, F.; Castañeda-Chávez, M.; Galaviz-Villa, I.; Hinojosa-Garro, D. and Ortega-Morales, B. (2016). Implications of extracellular polymeric substance matrices of microbial habitats

- associated with coastal aquaculture systems. *Water*, 8(9):369.
38. Tesoriere, L.; Butera, D.; Allegra, M.; Fazzari, M. and Livrea, M. A. (2005). Distribution of betalain pigments in red blood cells after consumption of cactus pear fruits and increased resistance of the cells to ex vivo induced oxidative hemolysis in humans. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 53(4):1266-1270.
 39. Ahmad, A.; Davies, J.; Randall, S.; Skinner, G. R. B. (1996). Antiviral properties of extract of *Opuntia streptacantha*. *Antiviral Research*, 30(2-3): 75-85.
 40. Loro, J. F.; Del Rio, I. and Perez-Santana, L. (1999). Preliminary studies of analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties of *Opuntia dillenii* aqueous extract. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 67(2):213-218.
 41. Cicero, A. F. G.; Derosa, G. and Gaddi, A. (2004). What do herbalists suggest to diabetic patients in order to improve glycemic control? Evaluation of scientific evidence and potential risks. *Acta Diabetologica*, 41(3):91-98.
 42. Ibanez-Camacho, R. and Roman-Ramos, R. (1979). Hypoglycemic effect of *Opuntia cactus*. *Archivos de Investigacion Medica*, 10(4):223-230.
 43. Ibanez-Camacho, R.; Meckes-Lozoya, M. and Mellado-Campos, V. (1983). The hypoglucemic effect of *Opuntia streptacantha* studied in different animal experimental models. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 7(2): 175-181.
 44. Frati-Munari, A. C.; Gordillo, B. E.; Altamirano, P. and Ariza, C. R. (1988). Hypoglycemic effect of *Opuntia streptacantha* Lemaire in NIDDM. *Diabetes Care*, 11(1):63-66.
 45. Frati, A. C.; Jiménez, E.; Ariza, C. R. (1990). Hypoglycemic effect of *Opuntia ficus indica* in non insulin dependent diabetes mellitus patients. *Phytotherapy Research*, 4(5):195-197.
 46. Gurbachan, S. and Felker, P. (1998). Cactus: New world foods. *Indian Horticulture*, 43(1):29-31.
 47. Fernández, M. L.; Lin, E. C.; Trejo, A. and McNamara, D. J. (1992). Prickly pear (*Opuntia* sp.) pectin reverses low density lipoprotein receptor suppression induced by a hypercholesterolemic diet in guinea pigs. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 122(12):2330-2340.
 48. Stintzing, F. C.; Schieber, A. and Carle, R. (2001). Phytochemical and nutritional significance of cactus pear. *European Food Research and Technology*, 212(4):396-407.
 49. Stintzing, F. C. and Carle, R. (2006). Cactus fruits-more than colour. *Fruit Processing*, 16:166-171.
 50. (<https://www.webmd.com/diet/health-benefits-cactus>)
 51. Blando, F., Russo, R., Negro, C., De Bellis, L., and Frassinetti, S. (2019). Antimicrobial and Antibiofilm Activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* of *Opuntia ficus-indica* (L.) Mill. Cladode Polyphenolic Extracts. *Antioxidants* (Basel, Switzerland), 8(5), 117. doi:10.3390/antiox8050117
 52. Ramírez-Moreno, E., Cariño-Cortés, R., Cruz-Cansino, N. d. S., Delgado-Olivares, L., Ariza-Ortega, J. A., Montañez-Izquierdo, V. Y., . . . Filardo-Kerstupp, T. (2017). Antioxidant and antimicrobial properties of cactus pear (*Opuntia*) seed oils. *Journal of Food Quality*, 2017.
 53. Philip, K., Malek, S. N., Sani, W., Shin, S. K., Kumar, S., Lai, H. S., . . . Rahman, S. N. (2009). Antimicrobial activity of some medicinal plants from Malaysia. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 6(8), 1613.
 54. Ahmad, A., Davies, J., Randall, S., and Skinner, G. (1996). Antiviral properties of extract of *Opuntia streptacantha*. *Antiviral Research*, 30(2-3), 75-85.
 55. Bensadón, S., Hervert-Hernández, D., Sáyago-Ayerdi, S. G., and Goñi, I. (2010). By-Products of *Opuntia ficus-indica* as a Source of Antioxidant Dietary Fiber. *Plant Foods for Human Nutrition*, 65(3), 210-216.
 56. Galati, E. M., Mondello, M. R., Giuffrida, D., Dugo, G., Miceli, N., Pergolizzi, S., and Taviano, M. F. (2003). Chemical Characterization and Biological No of Sicilian *Opuntia ficus indica* (L.) Mill. Fruit Juice: Antioxidant and Antiulcerogenic Activity. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 51(17), 4903-4908.
 57. López-Romero, P., Pichardo-Ontiveros, E., Avila-Nava, A., Vázquez-Manjarrez, N., Tovar, A. R., Pedraza-Chaverri, J., and Torres, N. (2014). The effect of nopal (*Opuntia ficus indica*) on postprandial blood glucose, incretins, and antioxidant activity in Mexican patients with type 2 diabetes after consumption of two different composition breakfasts. *J Acad Nutr Diet*, 114(11), 1811-1818.

58. Roman-Ramos, R., Flores-Saenz, J., and Alarcon-Aguilar, F. (1995). Anti-hyperglycemic effect of some edible plants. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 48(1), 25-32.
59. Alimi, H., Hfaiedh, N., Bouoni, Z., Hfaiedh, M., Sakly, M., Zourgui, L., and Rhouma, K. B. (2010). Antioxidant and antiulcerogenic activities of *Opuntia ficus indica* f. *inermis* root extract in rats. *Phytomedicine*, 17(14), 1120-1126. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2010.05.001>
60. Galati, E. M., Monforte, M. T., Tripodo, M. M., d'Aquino, A., and Mondello, M. R. (2001). Antiulcer activity of *Opuntia ficus indica* (L.) Mill. (Cactaceae): ultrastructural study. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 76(1), 1-9.
61. Linarès, E., Thimonier, C., and Degre, M. (2007). The effect of neopuntia® on blood lipid parameters—Risk factors for the metabolic syndrome (Syndrome χ). *Advances in Therapy*, 24(5), 1115-1125. doi:10.1007/BF02877717
62. Onakpoya, I. J., O'Sullivan, J., and Heneghan, C. J. (2015). The effect of cactus pear (*Opuntia ficus-indica*) on body weight and cardiovascular risk factors: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials. *Nutrition*, 31(5), 640-646.
63. Huang, X., Li, Q., Guo, L., and Yan, Z. (2008). Protection of Cactus Polysaccharide against H₂O₂-induced damage in the rat cerebral cortex and hippocampus*☆: Differences in time of administration. *Neural Regeneration Research*, 3(1), 14-18.
64. Huang, X., Li, Q., Li, H., and Guo, L. (2009). Neuroprotective and antioxidative effect of cactus polysaccharides in vivo and in vitro. *Cell Mol Neurobiol*, 29(8), 1211-1222 doi:10.1007/s10571-009-9417-z
65. Kim, J. H., Park, S. M., Ha, H. J., Moon, C. J., Shin, T. K., Kim, J. M., . . . Wie, M. B. (2006). *Opuntia ficus-indica* attenuates neuronal injury in in vitro and in vivo models of cerebral ischemia. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 104(1-2), 257-262.
66. Sudzuki F, Muñoz C, Berger H, 1993. El cultivo de la tuna (cactus pear). Departamento de Reproducción Agrícola. Universidad de Chile, Santiago.
67. Stintzing FC, SchieberA. CarleR.2000. Cactus pear—a promising component to functional food. *Obst Gemüse Kartoffelver (Fruit Vegetable Potato Process)* 85: 40–47.
68. Uchoa AF, Souza PAS, Zarate RML, Gomes-FilhoE,Campos FAP. 1998. Isolation and characterization of a reserve protein from the seeds of *Opuntia ficus-indica* (Cactaceae). *Brazilian J Med Biol Sci*. 31(6): 757-761.
69. El-Mostafa K, El-Kharrassi Y, Badreddine A, Andreoletti P, Vamecq J, El-Kebbaj M, Latruffe N, Lizard G, Nasser B, Cherkaoui-Malki M. 2014. Nopal cactus (*Opuntia ficus-indica*) as a source of bioactive compounds for nutrition, health and disease. *Molecules*. 19(9): 14879-14901.
70. <https://www.webmd.com/diet/health-benefits-cactus>
71. P://www.google.com/imgres?imgurl=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.icarda.org%2Fsites%2Fdefault%2Ffiles%2Fstyles%2Fdefault%2Fpublic%2Fimages%2F2019-04%2Fdscn9390-min.jpg%3Fitok%3DhFJjMs47%2C%2520https%3A%2F%2Fwww.icarda.org%2Fthemes%2Fcusto%2Ficarda%2Fshare-image.png&dtbnid=UZXDHe_3_YGB_Mandvet=1&imgrefurl=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.icarda.org%2Fmedia%2Fnews%2Fcactus-catching-india&docid=RA0ixYf41nE2QMandw=4608&h=3456&hl=en-US&source=sh%2Fx%2Fim%2Fm6%2F4
72. https://www.agrifarming.in/cactus-farming-cultivation-practices-of-cactus#:~:text=Only%20you%20need%20is%20a,quantity%20of%20water%20and%20maintenance))
73. <https://images.app.goo.gl/z1sXYh5jUSAaH7BM8>
74. Fathordoobady, F., Manap, M., Selamat, J., and Singh, A. (2019). Development of supercritical fluid extraction for the recovery of betacyanins from red pitaya fruit (*Hylocereus polyrhizus*) peel: a source of natural red pigment with potential antioxidant properties. *International Food Research Journal*, 26(3), 1023-1034.
75. Sharif, K., Rahman, M., Azmir, J., Shamsudin, S. H., Uddin, M., Fahim, T., and Zaidul, I. (2015). Ethanol modified supercritical carbon dioxide extraction of antioxidant rich extract from *Pereskia bleo*. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, 21, 1314-1322.
76. Espinosa-Muñoz, V., Roldán-Cruz, C., Hernández-Fuentes, A., Quintero-Lira, A.,

- Almaraz-Buendía, I., and Campos-Montiel, R. (2017). Ultrasonic-assisted extraction of phenols, flavonoids, and biocompounds with inhibitory effect against *Salmonella Typhimurium* and *Staphylococcus Aureus* from Cactus pear. *Journal of Food Process Engineering*, 40(2), e12358.
77. Kivrak, Ş., Kivrak, İ., and Karababa, E. (2018). Analytical evaluation of phenolic compounds and minerals of *Opuntia robusta* J.C. Wendl. and *Opuntia ficus-barbarica* A. Berger. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 21(1), 229-241.
78. Albano, C., Negro, C., Tommasi, N., Gerardi, C., Mita, G., Miceli, A., . . . Blando, F. (2015). Betalains, Phenols and Antioxidant Capacity in Cactus Pear [*Opuntia ficus-indica* (L.) Mill.] Fruits from Apulia (South Italy) Genotypes. *Antioxidants (Basel, Switzerland)*, 4(2), 269-280.
79. Betancourt, C., Cejudo-Bastante, M. J., Heredia, F. J., and Hurtado, N. (2017). Pigment composition and antioxidant capacity of betacyanins and betaxanthins fractions of *Opuntia dillenii* (Ker Gawl) Haw cactus fruit. *Food Research International*, 101, 173-179.
80. Mena, P., Tassotti, M., Andreu, L., Nuncio-Jáuregui, N., Legua, P., Del Rio, D., and Hernández, F. (2018). Phytochemical characterization of different prickly pear (*Opuntia ficus-indica* (L.) Mill.) cultivars and botanical parts: UHPLC-ESI-MSn metabolomics profiles and their chemometric analysis. *Food Research International*, 108, 301-308.
81. <https://images.app.goo.gl/UEMxTD3H6VAwMsxB9>
82. <https://images.app.goo.gl/9NmDmakJdunLooPX6>
83. <https://images.app.goo.gl/miWcq8gammGq6S6DA>
84. https://www.google.com/imgres?imgurl=https%3A%2F%2Fstrapi.myplantin.com%2Flarge_main_041538e5-ba08-4dc5-8cbb-e8b6cc30e00c.webp&id=pbCRE_ty1-cZNMandvet=1&imgrefurl=https%3A%2F%2Fmyplantin.com%2Fplant%2F898&docid=PsR22PMg_8OIMandw=750&dh=1000&hl=en-IN&source=sh%2Fx%2Fim%2Fm1%2F4
85. <https://images.app.goo.gl/hocKzMX8ndvGgTUd6>
86. <https://images.app.goo.gl/YCGdgcdV6P2YaNuw6>